

Studies on the Antibiotic Activity of Tea

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In vitro studies on the effect of infusions of green and black tea, their tannins, and individual catechins isolated from green tea leaves on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhosa*, *Shigella dysenteriae* and *El Tor vibrio* (an allied strain of *Vibrio cholerae*) have been made. Tannins of Indian tea have been found to possess considerable antibacterial activity towards micro-organisms causing intestinal disorder. Green tea tannins have been found to be more active than black tea tannins. Amongst all the individual catechins studied, (—)-epigallocatechin and (—)-epigallocatechin gallate have been found to possess remarkably stronger antibacterial action on the pathogenic organisms tested.

McNaught¹ by *in vitro* studies with pure culture of Typhoid bacilli observed that cold tea infusion possessed considerable bactericidal activity towards this test organism and recommended the use of cold tea infusion as a salutary substitute for water in the soldier's canteen during active service. Berdyeva² demonstrated the antibacterial action of tea on *Shigella paradysenteriae* (Type W). Bokuchava and Berdyeva³ showed the efficacy of tannins and strong infusion of Russian green tea in the treatment of dysentery by laboratory and clinical trials.

The present communication deals with the studies on the antimicrobial activity of Indian teas. In this connection the relative inhibiting effects of tea infusions (green and black), tannins, obtained from green and black tea, and individually isolated catechins like (—)-epicatechin, (—)-epigallocatechin, (—)-epicatechin gallate, and (—)-epigallocatechin gallate, which are the chief constituents of the tannins of green tea, on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *El Tor vibrio*, and, *Salmonella typhosa* have been studied. The term 'tannins' used here designates the ethyl acetate-soluble polyphenols of tea.

Although no inhibiting activity of green and black tea infusions (10%) on the growth of *Staph. aureus* has been observed (Table II) under the present experimental condition, actual plate-counts, have, however, revealed considerable activity of both⁴. In this case too, green tea infusion (10%) has been found to possess greater inhibiting power than black tea infusion of similar strength.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tea infusion was prepared by treating a known amount of powdered tea sample with 100 ml of boiling distilled water for 5 minutes. It was filtered and the volume of the filtrate

1. McNaught, *Tea & Coffee Trade J.*, 1923, July, p. 129.

2. Berdyeva, *Zhur. Microbiol. Epidemiol. Immunobiol.*, 1956, 27, No. 11, pp. 79-82.

3. Bokuchava and Berdyeva, *Biochim. Chisnogo Proizvodstva*, 1959, 7, 209.

4. Das, unpublished results.

with washings was made to 100 ml. Samples of green and black tea used in the present experiments were received from Dagapur Tea Estate, Siliguri, West Bengal, and Nalani Tea Estate, Assam, respectively. These tea samples were manufactured from leaves (Assam variety) of November, 1959 season.

Isolation of Tannins and Individual Catechins.—Green tea tannins and black tea tannins were prepared according to a modified method of Harrison⁵. The different types of individual catechins present in the tannin preparations, obtained from green and black tea, were determined by partitioning them on a paper chromatogram⁶ and subsequent elution of the spots revealed under ultraviolet light with a known volume of speck alcohol for estimating the concentrations of each catechin spectrophotometrically⁷ using the literature values of extinction coefficients⁸. The results of these analyses are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Composition of tannins obtained from green and black tea.

(Results are in mg./g. of ethyl acetate-soluble polyphenols and are average of six separate determinations.)

Test material.	(-)-Epi-catechin.	(+)-Catechin.	(-)-Epicatechin gallate.	(±)-Gallocatechin.	(-)-Epigallocatechin.	(-)-Epigallocatechin gallate.
Green tea tannins	35.2	29.3	51.5	50.4	97.6	340.7
Black tea tannins	31.3	32.0	38.1	15.5	Absent	51.3

(-)-Epicatechin and (-)-epicatechin gallate were isolated from green tea leaves according to the method of Tsujimura^{9,10}.

Measurement of Bacterial Growth Inhibition.—'Paper disc' method of Mitchell *et al*¹¹. with some modifications was used in these experiments for determining the sensitivity of micro-organisms towards tea polyphenols for its simplicity, rapidity, and reproducibility. Sharp circular paper discs (Whatman chromatography paper No. 3) of uniform diameter (14 mm), initially sterilized at 15 lbs./inch² for 15 minutes, were used by soaking them in solutions to be assayed so as to saturate them with the solutions (pH 6.8-7) of the respective test materials and placing aseptically with the help of a fine-tipped forceps, on the surface of a suitable agar medium (15 ml), inoculated in bulk heavily and uniformly from a 20 hour's broth culture or a prepared suspension of the test organism and set in Czechoslovakian petri plates (90 mm × 20mm).

*Received as gift samples from Dr. Tokino of Tokyo University of Education, Tokyo, Japan.

5. Harrison and Roberts, *Biochem. J.*, 1939, **33**, 1408.

6. Cartwright and Roberts, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 1354.

7. Bhatia and Ullah, *ibid.*, 1961, 1169.

8. Vukšić and Brandenberger, *J. Chromatog.*, 1959 **2**, 173.

9. *Sci. Paper Inst. Phys. Chem. Res.* (Tokyo), 1931, **15**, 158.

10. *Ibid.*, 1935, **20**, 186.

11. *Texas Reports on Biology and Medicine*, 1953, **2**, 122.

After placing the discs, the plates were refrigerated (15°) for 2 hours for facilitating complete diffusion of the test materials and later these were incubated at 37° for 18 hours. Following incubation, the plates were examined and the zone of inhibition was measured with the help of a millimeter scale. According to these measurements, the relative degree of susceptibility was classified as very sensitive (V.S. diam. 23 mm and over), sensitive (S. diam. 19—23 mm), moderately sensitive (M.S. diam. 17—19 mm), weakly sensitive (W.S. diam. 15—17 mm), and resistant (R. diam. 15 mm and under).

Although the zone size is known to depend on several factors¹², besides antimicrobial activity of an agent like (a) rate of diffusion of the agent through the medium, (b) amount of moisture, (c) rate of growth of organism, and (d) depth of the agar medium, it has been found by running plate-counts studies on the effect of test materials on the growth of micro-organisms in parallel with 'paper disc' method that the zone size, under the controlled experimental conditions followed here, represents the relative order of effectiveness in regard to the inhibiting power of the respective test materials.

Bacterial Cultures

(A) *Staphylococcus aureus*.—A culture of *Staphylococcus aureus* was maintained by weekly subculture on nutrient agar medium.

(B) *El Tor vibrio* PR 121.—A culture of *El Tor vibrio* received from Indian Institute for Biochemistry and Experimental Medicine, Calcutta, was maintained by weekly transfer on a medium.

(C) *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Salmonella typhosa*.—Cultures of these organisms received from the School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta, were maintained by weekly transfer on a medium. Compositions of the media used for the three cultures are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

(In g./100 ml distilled water).

	(A).	(B).	(C).
Bacto (Difco) peptone	0.5	0.5	1.0
Bacto (Difco) beef extract	0.3	..	0.5
Glucose	0.5	..	..
NaCl	..	1.0	0.5
Agar	1.5	1.5	1.5
Final pH	6.6-6.8	7.6-7.8	6.8-7.0

In all the cases, the composition of the inoculated basal medium for studying the growth of the different test organisms was the same as that of the respective maintenance medium.

Comparison of Inhibiting Power with known Antibiotics.—The inhibiting power of the different test materials, active against the growth of *Staph. aureus*, was com-

12. Ericsson, *Scand. J. Clin. Lab. Invest.*, 1954, 6, 2.

TABLE III

Effect of tea infusions, tannins, and separated individual catechins on the growth of micro-organisms.
(Each figure represents the average of six determinations).

Test material used.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus.</i>		<i>Shigella dysenteriae.</i>		<i>Salmonella typhosa.</i>		<i>El Tor vibrio.</i>		
	Conc.	Diam. Suscep. Equiv. Conc. of the tibility. zone.	Diam. Sus. †Equiv. Conc. of the cep- tibility. zone.	‡Equiv. acti- vity.	Diam. Suscep. †Equiv. of the tibility. zone.	‡Equiv. acti- vity.	*Conc. Diam. of the cephabi- lity. zone.	W.S.	
Green tea infusion	10%	— R	23.0mm V.S.	25.0	20%	23.2mm S	25.0	20%	16.8mm W.S.
Black tea infusion	"	— R	18.5 M.S.	14.0	"	18.8 M.S.	13.0	"	15.8 W.S.
Green tea tannins	10mg/ml	20.5mm S	0.46 5mg./ml	19.3 S	10mg./ml	21.5 S	22.0	10mg./ml.	16.5 W.S.
Black tea tannins	"	15.5 W.S.	0.20	15.0 W.S.	"	17.0 M.S.	9.0	"	— R
(-)-Epicatechin	"	18.0 M.S.	"	— R	"	14.5 R	"	"	15.5 W.S.
(-)-Epicatechin gallate	"	16.0 W.S.	"	— R	"	15.0 W.S.	"	"	17.0 M.S.
(-)-Epigallocatechin	"	24.0 V.S.	"	27.6 V.S.	"	18.0 M.S.	"	"	19.0 S
(-)-Epigallocatechin gallate	"	20.0 S	"	22.6 S	"	16.0 W.S.	"	"	20.7 S

* In terms of units of penicillin G/ml.

† In terms of µg. of chloramphenicol/ml.

N.B. Concentration refers to inhibiting zones.

"—" Indicates no visible inhibition under the present experimental conditions.

pared with that of penicillin G by using 'paper disc' method¹³ and was expressed in terms of units of penicillin G per ml. Inhibiting power of the materials, which had action on *Sh. dysenteriae* and *Salm. typhosa* was compared with that of chloramphenicol by using 'paper disc' method¹³ and expressed in terms of micrograms of chloramphenicol per ml. In absence of any suitable standard drug, the test materials, which showed inhibition against the growth of *El Tor vibrio* could not be compared as in the other cases. Results are recorded in Table III.

DISCUSSION

Table III shows that green tea tannins unlike black tea tannins possess considerably greater inhibiting activity towards *Staph. aureus*, *Sh. dysenteriae*, *Salm. typhosa*, and *El Tor vibrio*. The lower activity of black tea tannins seems to be due to oxidative changes¹⁴⁻¹⁶ of some of the active catechins (flavanols) during 'fermentation'. This will be evident from the contents of different types of catechin present in the tannin preparations obtained from green and black tea, as recorded in Table I. Amongst the individual catechins tested, (-)-epigallocatechin seems to possess maximum inhibiting power and (-)-epigallocatechin gallate stands next to (-)-epigallocatechin, so far as its inhibiting action towards *Staph. aureus*, *Sh. dysenteriae*, and *Salm. typhosa* is concerned.

It will also be evident from Table III that *Staph. aureus* is more susceptible towards (-)-epicatechin and (-)-epigallocatechin than their corresponding gallates. In case of *El Tor vibrio*, this strain is found to be more susceptible towards the gallates of (-)-epicatechin and (-)-epigallocatechin than the corresponding non-galloyl forms of these compounds. The relative order of susceptibility of this organism towards the various catechins can be arranged in decreasing order: (-)-epigallocatechin gallate > (-)-epigallocatechin > (-)-epicatechin gallate > (-)-epicatechin.

Further, moderately strong infusion (10-20%) of green tea is considerably inhibiting towards the growth of *Sh. dysenteriae*, *Salm. typhosa*, and *El Tor vibrio*. Similar infusion of black tea is, however, found to be less effective in regard to this. This is probably due to the very low content of (-)-epigallocatechin gallate, (-)-epicatechin gallate, ($\pm$)-gallocatechin, and complete absence of (-)-epigallocatechin in black tea. These polyphenols are oxidised^{14,16} during the 'fermentation' stage in the manufacture of this type of tea. The inhibiting property of tea, chiefly due to its content of tannins, has been confirmed by actual removal of the tannins from tea infusion by lead acetate and testing the antimicrobial activity of the tannin-free solution by 'paper disc' method. In that case, no activity could be detected.

13. Florey *et al.*, "Antibiotics", Vol I, Oxford Medical Publication, Oxford University Press, 1949.

14. Roberts and Williams, *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 1958, 9, 217.

15. Roberts, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1957, 1254.

16. Vuzatz and Brandenberger, *J. Chromatog.*, 1961, 5, 17.

That the caffeine constituent of tea shows no inhibiting activity at the concentration at which it occurs in the test infusion, has been confirmed by a separate experiment.

Results of the present study are supported in part by the findings of McNaught¹ and Berdyeva² so far as our studies with *Salm. typhosa* and *Sh. dysenteriae* respectively are concerned. Berdyeva working with *Shigella paradysenteriae* (type W), concluded that in comparison to Russian black tea, the Russian green tea was more inhibiting towards this organism.

Thus it appears that Indian tea tannins possess considerable antibacterial activity towards a number of micro-organisms causing common intestinal disorders. It seems that tea tannins might play a significant role in intestinal hygiene and prevention of infections by suppurative organisms.

Moreover, the role of green tea and its tannins, which are already known to possess considerable vitamin P activity³, in maintaining the integrity of the walls of the capillary system of the intestine affected during infection by *Vibrio cholerae*⁴ merits further investigation. Results of investigation along this line will be reported elsewhere.

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17. Bokuchava *et al.*, *Doklady, USSR*, 1950, 3, 52.

18. De and Chatterjee, *J. Path. & Bact.*, 1953, 66, 559.